

Anti-collagenase and anti-elastase activities of *Ardisia elliptica* Thunb. extract: *in vitro* and molecular docking insights

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Received 27 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 19 June 2026 ♦ Published 1 July 2026

Citation: Rosidah I, Ngatinem N, Subiantoro AH, Kusumaningrum S, Firdayani F, Wibowo AE, Mun'im A (2026) Anti-collagenase and anti-elastase activities of *Ardisia elliptica* Thunb. extract: *in vitro* and molecular docking insights. Pharmacia 73: e193264. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e193264>

Abstract

Ardisia elliptica Thunb. (AET) has been recognized as a source of natural active ingredients with antioxidant and anti-aging properties. However, its mode of action remains inadequately elucidated. This study aims to characterize the phytochemical profile and evaluate the antioxidant and collagenase- and elastase-inhibitory activities of AET extract *in vitro*, as well as elucidate the potential interaction mechanisms of the compounds with enzyme active sites through molecular docking. Different plant parts (leaves, flowers, and fruits) were extracted using 70% ethanol by ultrasound-assisted extraction followed by maceration. Phytochemical analysis encompassed the quantification of total phenolic and flavonoid contents and metabolite profiling using liquid chromatography coupled with Orbitrap high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS). Antioxidant activities were measured using 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) assays. The leaf extract demonstrated the highest total phenolic content and antioxidant activity, with IC_{50} values of 54.21 ± 2.21 and 43.73 ± 0.64 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for DPPH and ABTS, respectively. Furthermore, it showed significant collagenase- and elastase-inhibitory activities, with IC_{50} values of 104.11 ± 11.20 and 294.67 ± 8.52 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. Its collagenase-inhibitory activity was comparable to that of the positive control, epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), but remained lower for elastase inhibition. Additionally, molecular docking predicted the strong potential of bilobol, α -linolenic acid, and monoolein as collagenase inhibitors, with MolDock scores of -131 , -121 , and -119 , respectively. Monoolein, bilobol, and erucamide exhibited potential elastase-inhibitory activity, with MolDock scores of -139 , -133 , and -129 , respectively. These findings highlight AET leaf extract as a promising natural candidate for the development of phytocosmetic products, particularly for anti-aging applications with collagenase- and elastase-inhibitory mechanisms.

Keywords

anti-collagenase, anti-elastase, antioxidant, *Ardisia elliptica*, molecular docking

Introduction

Skin is the largest organ in the body and mediates interactions between the internal physiological system and environmental factors. A wide range of environmental factors, such as sun exposure, chemical pollution, and nutritional levels, can stimulate the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the skin. These factors can alter the structure and function of the epidermis and dermis, thereby accelerating skin aging (Eun et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021; Lee et al. 2021). Oxidative stress contributes to the degradation of the extracellular matrix (ECM) by inhibiting the synthesis of structural components such as collagen and elastin while simultaneously activating degrading enzymes, including collagenase and elastase (Chaikhong et al. 2022).

Collagen is a major component of the ECM, comprising approximately 70–80% of the skin's dry weight, and plays a crucial role in maintaining the strength and structure of the dermis (Tzaphlidou 2004; Shin et al. 2019). Elastin plays a role in maintaining the elasticity of the skin, although it is a minor component, accounting for 2–4% of the ECM. ROS overproduction can reduce the synthesis of new collagen and decrease collagen and elastin levels in the dermis (Wei et al. 2024). This process contributes to the appearance of signs of aging, such as wrinkles, sagging, and loss of skin elasticity (Shin et al. 2019; Cruz et al. 2023). Therefore, most anti-aging interventions are designed to target ROS scavenging and inhibit collagenase and elastase activities.

Maintaining collagen and elastin levels is a crucial focus in the development of anti-aging skin agents, particularly through approaches that suppress ECM degradation (Lee et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2025). Bioactive compounds derived from plants are known to have the potential to maintain the integrity of collagen and elastin, thereby slowing the skin aging process (Younis et al. 2022; Rungruang et al. 2025). Furthermore, the antioxidant activity of plants also offers a potential approach to combat skin aging caused by ROS (Pientaweeratch et al. 2016; Chaikhong et al. 2022). Phenolic compounds, including anthocyanins, flavonoids, and phenolic acids in plants, have been reported to possess activities linked to skin protection. They inhibit the activity of aging-related enzymes and exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-collagenase, and anti-elastase effects (Deniz et al. 2020; Jo et al. 2020; Buraphaka et al. 2022; Păcularu-Burada et al. 2024). Additionally, fatty acids have been noted for their anti-aging properties, particularly their anti-collagenase and anti-elastase activities (Vu et al. 2021; Younis et al. 2022).

Ardisia elliptica Thunb. (AET), commonly known as lampeni in Indonesia, is traditionally used to treat chest pain, fever, diarrhea, gastric disorders, liver poisoning, and cancer (Alias and Ishak 2014; Fadhillah et al. 2022). Scientifically, AET exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, and antibacterial properties (Al-Abd et al. 2017; Chatatikun and Chiabchalard 2017; Buraphaka et al. 2022). Despite evidence of collagenase-inhibitory activity in AET (Chatatikun and Chiabchalard 2017), the specific compound responsible remains unelucidated, and its activity against elastase has not been investigated.

Therefore, this study investigated the phytochemical constituents of AET, focusing on its antioxidant properties and activities against collagenase and elastase, which are associated with anti-aging effects. The compound profile of AET was characterized using liquid chromatography coupled with Orbitrap high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS). Additionally, the extract's capability to inhibit skin aging enzymes, specifically collagenase and elastase, was evaluated. Furthermore, the interactions between the bioactive compounds of AET extract and their targets were explored through molecular docking. This comprehensive approach was utilized to aid in the development of phytocosmetic products, specifically targeting anti-aging applications.

Materials and methods

Plant materials

The leaves, fruits, and flowers of AET were collected in January 2025 from Kebun Percobaan Anak Tuha BRIN, Lampung, Indonesia (−4.9551, 105.0683). The plant material was taxonomically identified as *Ardisia elliptica* Thunb., family Primulaceae, by Arifin Surya Dwipa Irsyam, S.Si., M.Si., a botanist at the School of Life Sciences and Technology, Institut Teknologi Bandung (ITB), with the identification number 862/ITI.C11.2/TA.00/2025. The voucher specimen was deposited in the Laboratory for the Development of Industrial Technology for Agriculture and Biomedical, the National Research and Innovation Agency (LAPTIAB-BRIN).

Chemicals and reagents

Collagenase from *Clostridium histolyticum*, *N*-[3-(2-furyl)acryloyl]-Leu-Gly-Pro-Ala (FALGPA), elastase from porcine pancreas, *N*-succinyl-Ala-Ala-Ala-*p*-nitroanilide (AAPVN), calcium chloride, epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), ascorbic acid, gallic acid (GA), quercetin, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, aluminum chloride, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Tris-HCl was purchased from Promega. Methanol and ethanol were purchased from Merck, USA. All solvents used were of analytical grade. Ethanol for the extraction process of AET was obtained from Indo Acidatama, Indonesia.

Extraction of *A. elliptica*

Dry powders of leaves (100 g), flowers (25 g), and fruits (50 g) of AET were each extracted independently. Each plant part was individually mixed with 70% ethanol at a material-to-solvent ratio of 1:15 (w/v), yielding 1,500 mL, 375 mL, and 750 mL of solvent for leaves, flowers, and fruits, respectively. Each mixture was subjected to sonication for 15 min, employing a power of 1,375 W, a frequency of 20 kHz, and an amplitude of 20% using an ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) probe and booster

(Qsonic AdeLab, Australia). Following this, the mixture was subjected to maceration for 30 min at room temperature with occasional stirring. The resulting extracts were then filtered and concentrated separately using a rotary vacuum evaporator, and the residues were weighed to determine the percentage yield from the plant material. The yields from the AET leaves, flowers, and fruits were $25.61 \pm 5.62\%$, $15.42 \pm 4.75\%$, and $38.93 \pm 11.66\%$, respectively.

Determination of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of AET extract was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method, as outlined in the Farmakope Herbal Indonesia (Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia 2017), with slight modifications. The extracts were dissolved in ethanol at varying concentrations: leaf extract at 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, flower extract at 1,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and fruit extract at 2,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The assay was conducted by adding 25 μL of sample to a 96-well microplate and mixing it with 75 μL of 7.5% Folin–Ciocalteu reagent, allowing it to react for 8 min at room temperature. Then, 100 μL of 1% sodium hydroxide solution was added to the mixture. The solution was then incubated in the dark at room temperature for 90 min. Absorbance was measured at 730 nm using a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments, Germany). The total phenolic content was determined using a standard curve of GA across a concentration range of 12.5–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The total phenolic content was calculated and expressed as mg GA equivalent per gram of extract (mg GAE/g extract).

Determination of total flavonoid content

The total flavonoid content was determined using the aluminum chloride method (Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia 2017), with slight modifications. The AET extracts were dissolved in ethanol at varying concentrations: leaf and fruit extracts at 2,500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and flower extract at 5,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Briefly, 25 μL of AET extract was added and mixed with 20 μL of 10% aluminum chloride hexahydrate, 20 μL of 1 M sodium acetate, and 100 μL of water in a 96-well microplate. The mixture was incubated for 30 min at room temperature, and the absorbance was read at 425 nm using a microplate reader. Quercetin was used as the standard to determine the total flavonoid content values of the samples. A standard curve was prepared using concentrations of quercetin in the 10–60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ range, and the total flavonoid content values are presented as mg quercetin equivalent per gram of extract (mg QE/g extract).

Antioxidant assay

Antioxidant activity assay using the DPPH method

The DPPH radical-scavenging activity of AET extracts was determined using the method of Rusmana et al. (2017), with some modifications. Each extract was prepared in various concentrations (leaf and flower extracts, 6.25–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$;

fruit extract, 100–800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$; and ascorbic acid, 3.12–25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Briefly, 50 μL of AET extract was placed in 96-well plates. The reaction was initiated by adding 150 μL of DPPH solution (0.1 mM in methanol). The mixture was left to stand at room temperature for 30 min. The absorbance values of the final solution were read at 517 nm using a microplate reader.

Antioxidant activity assay using the ABTS method

The ABTS radical-scavenging activity assay was performed for AET extracts as described by Rusmana et al. (2017), with some modifications. To generate the ABTS radicals, 7.14 mM ABTS and 4.9 mM potassium persulfate were combined at a 1:1 volume ratio, followed by incubation for 16 h in the dark at room temperature before use. The radical solution was diluted with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at pH 7.4 until the absorbance was 0.70 ± 0.05 at 745 nm. The leaf extract was tested at 6.25–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$; fruit and flower extracts were tested at 12.5–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$; and ascorbic acid was evaluated at 3.12–50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. All assays were performed in triplicate. Briefly, 50 μL of sample was added to each well of a 96-well microplate, followed by the addition of 150 μL of fresh ABTS solution, and the mixture was allowed to stand for 6 min in the dark at room temperature. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 745 nm.

In vitro anti-aging assay

Inhibition of collagenase activity

Collagenase-inhibitory activity was evaluated based on the method of Shirzad et al. (2018), with some modifications. A mixture of 30 μL of sample at various concentrations, 50 μL of Tris-HCl buffer (50 mM, pH 7.4, containing 0.36 mM calcium chloride), and 20 μL of collagenase (800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in a 96-well microplate was pre-incubated for 20 min at 37 °C. After pre-incubation, 20 μL of 2 mM FAL-GPA was added and incubated for 30 min at 37 °C. Absorbance was measured using a microplate reader at 340 nm. EGCG was used as a positive control, and the solvent was used as a negative control. The collagenase inhibition assay was performed in triplicate. The collagenase-inhibitory activity of AET extract was interpreted as the IC_{50} value.

Inhibition of elastase activity

Elastase-inhibitory activity was measured based on the method of Widowati et al. (2020), with modifications. In a 96-well plate, a mixture of 25 μL of samples at various concentrations, 50 μL of Tris-HCl buffer (100 mM, pH 8), and 12.5 μL of elastase from porcine pancreas (40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ in cold water) was pre-incubated for 15 min at 37 °C. The solution was then supplemented with 12.5 μL of AAAPVN substrate and incubated for an additional 15 min at 37 °C. Absorbance was measured using a microplate reader at 410 nm. EGCG was used as a positive control in this assay, while the solvent was used as the negative control. The IC_{50} values of the AET extract were determined and reported as the mean \pm SD from the experiments.

Phytochemical analysis of the *A. elliptica* leaf extract

The identification of phytochemical content in the AET leaf extract was performed using liquid chromatography (Thermo Scientific™ Vanquish™ UHPLC Binary Pump) and Orbitrap high-resolution mass spectrometry (Thermo Scientific™ Q Exactive™ Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap™ High Resolution Mass Spectrometer) (Windarsih et al. 2022). Liquid chromatography was carried out using a Thermo Scientific™ Accucore™ Phenyl-Hexyl analytical column (100 mm × 2.1 mm ID × 2.6 μm). The mobile phases were MS-grade water containing 0.1% formic acid (A) and MS-grade acetonitrile containing 0.1% formic acid (B), employing the gradient technique with a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. Mobile phase B was set at 5%, increased gradually to 90% in 16 min, maintained at 90% for 4 min, and returned to the initial condition (5% B) until 25 min. The column temperature was set to 40 °C, and the injection volume was 3 μL. Non-targeted screening was carried out using full MS/dd-MS² acquisition mode in positive and negative ionization modes. Nitrogen was used for the sheath, auxiliary, and sweep gases, which were set to 32, 8, and 4 arbitrary units (AU), respectively. The spray voltage was 3.30 kV, the capillary temperature was set to 320 °C, and the auxiliary gas heater temperature was set to 30 °C. The scan range was *m/z* 66.7–1,000, and the resolution was 70,000 for full MS and 17,500 for dd-MS², both in positive and negative ions.

Molecular docking studies

The collagenase structure was selected as previously reported by Ajayi et al. (2024), while the elastase structure was obtained according to Rungruang et al. (2025). Three-dimensional structures of collagenase (PDB ID: 1HFC) and elastase (PDB ID: 1BRU) were obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. The ligand molecular structures of phytochemical compounds from AET leaf extract and the standard compound used in this study, EGCG (Compound CID: CID 65064), were obtained from PubChem. The Molegro Virtual Docker 6.0 platform (MVD; Molegro Aps, Aarhus C, Denmark) was used to estimate the inhibitory action mechanism of each bioactive ligand bound to the substrate-binding site of collagenase and elastase, which predicts experimental binding (Rosidah et al. 2025). The lowest-energy conformation of each compound was stored in mol2 format as a prerequisite for MVD. Protein and ligand structures were prepared using the built-in preparation tool before docking and interaction analysis. The binding sites of both enzymes were manually defined using the user-defined cavity option in MVD. The docking center of collagenase was set at coordinates $x = 26.59$, $y = 21.74$, and $z = 23.05$, with a radius of 9 Å, whereas elastase was defined at $x = 22.97$, $y = 47.76$, and $z = 16.92$, with a radius of 5 Å. Validation was performed by re-docking each native ligand to the active site of the corresponding enzyme. The objective was to

confirm that the native ligand binds precisely to the active site cleft with minimal deviation compared to the original co-crystallized complex (Rungruang et al. 2025). The re-docked complexes were superimposed onto their corresponding native co-crystallized structures, and the root mean square deviation (RMSD) values between the native and re-docked poses were calculated to evaluate docking reliability. After validation, docking simulations of all compounds were performed using the MolDock Optimizer algorithm under default docking parameters to obtain the best binding poses. Protein–ligand interactions were subsequently visualized using BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer v21.1.0.20298 (Accelrys, San Diego, CA, USA).

Statistical analysis

All results are expressed as the mean ± standard deviation (SD) of three results obtained. The IC₅₀ values of antioxidant and anti-aging activities were statistically analyzed using the slope of the scatter plot in Excel. To determine the level of significance of the mean values, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test or the Kruskal–Wallis test was performed to analyze all parameters, followed by the Bonferroni test. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered to indicate statistical significance.

Results and discussion

Total phenolic contents of the *A. elliptica* extracts

The leaf, flower, and fruit extracts of AET exhibited total phenolic content values of 214.72 ± 1.98 , 201.23 ± 5.66 , and 35.30 ± 2.57 mg GAE/g extract, respectively (Table 1). Among them, the leaf and flower extracts exhibited the highest phenolic contents. This finding is consistent with previous reports on species such as *Ardisia humilis* from Indonesia. In these studies, the methanol extract obtained through sonication of the leaves (155.20 mg GAE/g extract) and flowers (111.71 mg GAE/g extract) demonstrated a higher total phenolic content compared to the methanol extract of the fruit (42.76 mg GAE/g extract) from *A. humilis* (Rahayu et al. 2026). Such an increase may occur because the leaves and flowers are parts of the plant that are more readily exposed to UV radiation. This exposure leads to higher concentrations of phenolic acid and flavonoid compounds, which serve protective functions in these parts compared to the fruits (Safrina et al. 2022; Savina et al. 2023).

In contrast, other studies indicate different findings for *A. elliptica*. For instance, research conducted in Malaysia found that the methanol extracts of AET fruit and leaves, prepared using the maceration method, demonstrated higher phenolic content in the fruit extract compared to the leaf extract, with values of 71 and 37 mg GAE/g extract, respectively (Al-Abd et al. 2017). Furthermore, a study in Thailand reported that the methanol extract of AET fruit,

Table 1. Total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and antioxidant activities of *A. elliptica* extracts.

Sample	Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g extract)	Total flavonoid content (mg QE/g extract)	Antioxidant activities (IC ₅₀) (µg/mL)	
			DPPH	ABTS
Leaf extract	214.72 ± 1.98	5.46 ± 0.26	54.22 ± 2.21 ^b	43.73 ± 0.64 ^b
Flower extract	201.23 ± 5.66	3.08 ± 0.13	106.12 ± 2.78 ^b	136.49 ± 1.17 ^b
Fruit extract	35.30 ± 2.57	2.21 ± 0.15	442.99 ± 33.91 ^b	125.56 ± 3.38 ^b
Ascorbic acid	NA	NA	15.23 ± 0.14 ^a	24.60 ± 0.17 ^a

Data are expressed as means ± SD ($n = 3$); values with the same lowercase letters in the same column indicate no significant difference at $p < 0.05$. NA = not analyzed.

obtained through sonication, contained 38.04 ± 1.98 mg GAE/g dry weight of phenols, which is higher than the 12.98 ± 0.66 mg GAE/g dry weight found in the leaves (Buraaphaka et al. 2022). This discrepancy may be attributed to the fruit having a pulp matrix that is rich in water and soluble sugars, such as glucose and fructose. During drying, water loss, matrix shrinkage, sugar-related reactions, and enzymatic activity may contribute to phenolic degradation, leading to lower phenolic content (Kumar et al. 2022; Bayram et al. 2024). Additionally, different factors affecting phenolic compounds include genetic and environmental parameters (Liu et al. 2018). These findings suggest that AET extracts represent promising sources of natural phenolic compounds with potential antioxidant applications.

Total flavonoid contents of the *A. elliptica* extracts

The total flavonoid contents in the leaf, flower, and fruit extracts of AET were 5.46 ± 0.26 , 3.08 ± 0.13 , and 2.21 ± 0.15 mg QE/g extract, respectively (Table 1), with the leaf extract exhibiting the highest value. Flavonoids represent a significant subclass of phenolic compounds. In contrast, the flavonoid content values were considerably lower than the corresponding phenolic content in all extracts. This indicates that flavonoids are only a portion of the total phenolic constituents. In Table 2, LC-HRMS analysis tentatively identified flavonoids, specifically hyperoside, trifolin, and quercetin, with mzCloud best match confidence values of 80–100%, which is in line with the relatively low total flavonoid content values measured. These results indicate that non-flavonoid phenolic compounds also contribute substantially to the antioxidant properties of the extracts.

Antioxidant activity assay using the DPPH and ABTS method

Based on Table 1, AET leaf, flower, and fruit extracts exhibited DPPH free radical-scavenging activities with IC₅₀ values of 54.22 ± 2.2 , 106.12 ± 2.78 , and 442.99 ± 33.91 µg/mL, respectively. In addition, ascorbic acid, as a positive control, exhibited an IC₅₀ value of 15.23 ± 0.14 µg/mL. In the ABTS assay, the leaf extract exhibited the highest antioxidant activity, with an IC₅₀ value of 43.73 ± 0.64 µg/mL, followed by the fruit (125.56 ± 3.38 µg/mL) and flower (136.49 ± 1.17 µg/mL) extracts, whereas ascorbic acid exhibited an IC₅₀

value of 24.60 ± 0.17 µg/mL. The leaf extract of AET exhibited significant antioxidant activity, classified as strong antioxidant activity (DPPH, 50–100 µg/mL) and very strong antioxidant activity (ABTS, < 50 µg/mL) according to its IC₅₀ classification (Fatimawali et al. 2025).

The AET leaf extract demonstrated the highest antioxidant activities, exhibiting greater total phenolic and total flavonoid contents compared to extracts from flowers and fruits. This suggests that antioxidant capacity is primarily influenced by the accumulation of phenolic compounds, including flavonoids. The LC-HRMS analysis in Table 2 showed that flavonoid compounds, such as hyperoside, trifolin, and quercetin, as well as non-flavonoid phenolic compounds, such as gallic acid, *d*- α -tocopherol, 4-methoxycinnamaldehyde, and bilobol (alkylphenol), work synergistically to enhance antioxidant activity. The organ-specific accumulation of protective compounds in leaves likely contributes to their stronger antioxidant activity.

The DPPH and ABTS methods work through mixed mechanisms, which may explain the strong antioxidant activity observed in AET leaf extract (Munteanu and Apetrei 2021). Among the identified phenolic compounds, gallic acid is a potent plant antioxidant. Therefore, the antioxidant activity of AET may be attributed to the presence of these compounds, which exhibit mechanisms of action via hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) and single electron transfer (SET). The HAT mechanism involves the transfer of a hydrogen atom from a phenolic compound to a free radical. In the SET mechanism, the phenolic compound is converted into its radical cation by donating an electron to the radical. The hydroxyl group has been identified as the source of the radical scavenging activity of gallic acid, with the adjacent hydroxyl group contributing to the stabilization of the resulting species (Mittal et al. 2023). This correlation between antioxidant capacity and phenolic content has been consistently reported in AET and other medicinal plant species (Wong et al. 2020; Dirgantara et al. 2022).

Collagenase and elastase activity inhibition

The AET leaf extract was selected for testing collagenase- and elastase-inhibitory activity based on the results of total phenolic content and antioxidant activity. The results demonstrated inhibitory activity against collagenase and elastase, as presented in Fig. 1. The extract of AET leaves demonstrated inhibition of collagenase, with an IC₅₀ value

Table 2. Tentative identification of compounds from the leaf extract of *A. elliptica* using LC-HRMS.

No.	RT [min]	Compounds	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight	mzCloud Best Match Confidence (%)	Class
1	14.41	α -Linolenic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	278.22	100	Fatty acid
2	19.08	4-Phenylbutyric acid	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	164.08	98.8	Fatty acid
3	12.36	1-Linoleoyl glycerol	C ₂₁ H ₃₈ O ₄	354.28	98.4	Fatty acid
4	11.98	Monoolein	C ₂₁ H ₄₀ O ₄	356.29	98.4	Fatty acid
5	16.66	Linolenic acid ethyl ester	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ O ₂	306.26	98.4	Fatty acid
6	1.22	Gallic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	170.02	95.9	Phenolic
7	1.01	Citric acid	C ₆ H ₈ O ₇	192.03	95.5	Carboxylic acid
8	15.17	5-[(Z)-Pentadec-8-enyl]benzene-1,3-diol (Bilobol)	C ₂₁ H ₃₄ O ₂	318.26	94	Alkylphenol
9	5.68	Hyperoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₂	464.10	93.2	Flavonoid
10	17.01	Erucamide	C ₂₂ H ₄₃ NO	337.33	92.7	Fatty acid
11	19.07	D- α -Tocopherol	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂	430.38	90.2	Phenolic
12	6.19	Trifolin	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	448.10	89	Flavonoid
13	7.49	2-(2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxy-4H-chromen-4-one	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	302.04	88.2	Flavonoid
14	15.37	1-Stearoylglycerol	C ₂₁ H ₄₂ O ₄	358.31	87.5	Fatty acid
15	14.54	Hexadecanamide	C ₁₆ H ₃₃ NO	255.26	82.6	Fatty acid
16	14.83	4-Methoxycinnamaldehyde	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	162.07	80.2	Phenolic
17	6.42	Triethylene glycol monobutyl ether	C ₁₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	206.15	80.8	Ester glycol

Compounds were identified based on MS/MS spectral matching against the mzCloud database using Compound Discoverer software with accurate mass measurement (< 5 μ g/mL) and mzCloud best match confidence values of 80–100%.

Figure 1. Enzyme-inhibitory activity of the *A. elliptica* leaf extract and EGCG. **A.** Collagenase inhibition; **B.** Elastase inhibition. The IC₅₀ values with the same lowercase letters indicate no significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

of $104.11 \pm 11.20 \mu\text{g/mL}$, which is comparable to EGCG as the positive control (IC₅₀ = $111.11 \pm 3.50 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Nevertheless, some research has reported rare cases of allergic contact dermatitis associated with gallate derivatives in topical products (Holcomb et al. 2017; Khan et al. 2019). Moreover, EGCG has been associated with adverse effects, such as erythema and papular lesions (Stratton et al. 2000), highlighting the need for safer plant-derived alternatives. Previous research indicates that the ethanol extract of AET inhibits collagenase, exhibiting an IC₅₀ value of $157.78 \mu\text{g/mL}$ (Chatatikun and Chiabchalard 2017). Compared to those findings, the ethanolic extract of AET leaves demonstrated stronger inhibitory potency, as indicated by its lower IC₅₀ value. EGCG contains hydroxyl groups that enable hydrogen and hydrophobic interac-

tions with proteins, which together influence significant changes in the conformation of collagenase, resulting in high inhibition of its activity (Madhan et al. 2007). Molecular docking analysis further supports this interaction mechanism. While EGCG demonstrated inhibitory activity through this interaction, the stronger inhibitory potency observed in AET leaf extract may result from the synergistic effect of its active compounds.

Beyond collagenase inhibition, the extract also inhibited elastase, with an IC₅₀ value of $294.67 \pm 8.52 \mu\text{g/mL}$, whereas EGCG had an IC₅₀ value of $57.99 \pm 3.44 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Wittenauer et al. (2015) reported that the inhibition of elastase activity was significantly lower for individual polyphenols (EGCG, gallic acid, catechin, and procyanidin) compared to the inhibition of collagenase activity. The low inhibito-

ry effects of these polyphenols on elastase suggested that a nonspecific complexation reaction can be ruled out as the underlying mechanism of inhibition (Wittenauer et al. 2015). To date, no studies have precisely assessed the elastase-inhibitory activity of AET extract. Consequently, the present findings provide the first experimental evidence of its capacity to inhibit the elastase enzyme.

Phytochemical composition of the *A. elliptica* leaf extract

LC-HRMS analysis was used to identify the compounds in AET leaf extract. LC-HRMS allows for the elucidation of small molecules in the sample. This analysis yielded predictions regarding the identification of the detected substances using the mzCloud database. The mzCloud database houses MS and MS/MS spectra collected for various molecules, which are used as references for identifying unknown compounds. Compound identification was performed using Compound Discoverer software, which compares recorded fragmentation and molecular ion patterns with the mzCloud database and assigns a match score from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating a greater number of matched ions (Windarsih et al. 2022; Dewi et al. 2025)

LC-HRMS results showed that 17 compounds in the AET leaf extract were tentatively identified using the mzCloud best match confidence level of 80–100% (Table 2). The presence of gallic acid in *Ardisia* species has been reported. Gallic acid was detected in the fruit water extract of *Ardisia colorata* (Sumino et al. 2002) and a 75% ethanol leaf extract of *Ardisia compressa* (de Mejía et al. 2006). In addition, phenolic compounds such as bilobol have been reported in methanol extracts from the roots of *Ardisia brevicaulis* and rhizomes of *Ardisia gigantifolia* (Liu et al. 2009; Bao et al. 2010). Alpha-tocopherol was detected in the leaves and fruit of AET, influencing bioactivities, such as antioxidant and antibacterial activities (Al-Abd et al. 2017). Notably, several flavonoid compounds, such as quercetin, hyperoside, and trifolin, show antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-aging effects (Mapoung et al. 2021; Buraphaka et al. 2022; Park et al. 2025). In addition, monoolein, α -linolenic acid, and erucamide are known to be fatty acid compounds. Fatty acids exhibit various activities relevant to skin aging, including anti-elastase, anti-collagenase, and antioxidant activities (Rennert and Melzig 2002; Hwang et al. 2024).

Additionally, compounds were selected for docking analysis based on a combination of high mzCloud best match confidence scores (80–100%), accurate mass measurement, isotope pattern analysis, and previously reported biological activities relevant to the pharmacological targets being studied. However, it should be acknowledged that the identified metabolites represent tentative annotations, as confirmation using authentic reference standards was not performed. Furthermore, quantitative profiling of major constituents was not conducted, which may limit the robustness of compound selection for docking analysis. These aspects are recognized as limitations of the current study, and future investigations should in-

clude quantitative characterization and confirmation with authentic standards to provide a more comprehensive phytochemical basis for compound prioritization.

Molecular docking of bioactive compounds of *A. elliptica* leaf extract against collagenase and elastase activities

A molecular docking study was conducted to model the interaction of the dominant compounds in AET leaf extract with collagenase and elastase enzymes. Before the docking simulation, the docking parameters were examined to determine the optimal conditions by re-docking the native ligand into its respective active site. The validation analysis of the docking indicated that the RMSD values for the native ligand were 1.87 Å for collagenase (PDB CID: 1HFC) and 1.35 Å for elastase (PDB CID: 1BRU), both less than the 2 Å threshold, indicating that the docking procedure was valid (Wang et al. 2019). Fig. 2 shows the molecular structures of the overlay of the native ligand (co-crystal) and the re-docking results.

The docking scores for 17 compounds against collagenase enzymes, along with the amino acid residues involved and hydrogen and hydrophobic bonding interactions, are presented in Table 3. The docking results indicated that the top three compounds based on MolDock score were 5-[(Z)-pentadec-8-enyl]benzene-1,3-diol (bilobol), which showed strong binding affinity with a docking value of -131, followed by α -linolenic acid (-121) and monoolein (-119). In comparison, the native ligand and EGCG, used as a reference inhibitor for collagenase, showed MolDock scores of -139 and -128, respectively. These data indicate that EGCG had relatively strong inhibitory potential, approaching that of the positive control. More negative values indicate stronger binding stability between the receptor and ligand (Rosidah et al. 2025). Of the three top-ranked phytochemicals, only α -linolenic acid has been examined previously in docking studies on collagenase, where the discussion was mainly limited to binding affinity (Bakir Boga et al. 2023). In this study, interactions were also analyzed at the residue level, providing a clearer understanding of how the compound may bind within the active site. Based on Table 3 and Fig. 3, bilobol exhibited a strong binding interaction with collagenase through hydrogen bonds with amino acids in the active site, namely Asn180, Leu181, Ala182, Glu219, and His218, several of which overlap with those of the native ligand and EGCG. Meanwhile, monoolein interacted with the active site residue, Asn180. Alpha-linolenic acid formed interactions with collagenase at residue His218. The present findings therefore provide novel preliminary evidence of its potential binding affinity toward the enzyme. Hydrogen bonds play a crucial role in the stability of ligand-protein complexes, with their number positively correlating with both binding energy and interaction selection (Rosidah et al. 2025). Meanwhile, hydrophobic interactions with amino acids were observed in bilobol, namely His218 and Leu181, whereas the native ligand had hydrophobic interactions with amino acids His218, Leu181, His222, His228, and Val215. Moreover, monoolein, α -linolenic acid, and EGCG exhibited hydrophobic interactions with

Figure 2. Superimposition of poses between the native ligands during the validation procedure. **A.** Collagenase receptor (PDB ID: 1HFC) structure with the native ligand methylamino-phenylalanyl-leucyl-hydroxamic acid (RMSD 1.87 Å); **B.** Elastase receptor (PDB ID: 1BRU) structure with its native ligand 2-(2-hydroxy-cyclopentyl)-pent-4-enal (RMSD value of 1.35 Å). Blue color indicates before validation, and yellow color indicates after validation.

Figure 3. Three-dimensional and two-dimensional protein–ligand interactions at the collagenase-related active site of compounds from *A. elliptica* leaf extract. **A, B.** Native ligand methylamino-phenylalanyl-leucyl-hydroxamic acid; **C, D.** Bilobolol; **E, F.** α-Linolenic acid; **G, H.** Monoolein. **I, J.** EGCG.

Table 3. Hydrogen and hydrophobic interactions of target compounds from *A. elliptica* leaf extract with collagenase.

No.	Compounds	MolDock Score	Interaction	
			Hydrogen	Hydrophobic
1	Methylamino-phenylalanyl-leucyl-hydroxamic acid	-139	Asn180, Leu181, Pro238, Glu219, Ala182, His218	His218, Leu181, His222, His228, Val215
2	α -Linolenic acid	-121	Arg214, His218 , Thr241, Tyr237, Ser239, Tyr240	Val215, Leu181, His218,
3	4-Phenylbutyric acid	-86	Asn180, Ala182, Glu219	His218, Ser23, Tyr240, Val215
4	1-Linoleylglycerol	-117	Arg214, Glu219 , Tyr237, Val215, Ser239	Leu181
5	Monoolein	-119	Asn180, Asp175	Ala18, Val215, Leu18, His218
6	Linolenic acid ethyl ester	-105	Arg214, His218 , Thr241, Tyr237, Ser239, Tyr240	Val215, Leu181, His218
7	Gallic acid	-82	Leu181, Ala182, Arg214, His218, Tyr240, Glu219, Pro238	Leu181, Val215
8	Citric acid	-74	Arg214, Tyr240, Pro238, Ala182 , Tyr237	-
9	Bilobol	-131	Asn180, Leu181, Ala182 , Tyr240, Gly179, Glu219, His218 , His222, His228, Ser239	Gly179, Asn180, Leu181 , Tyr210, His218
10	Hyperoside	-104	Ala182 , Tyr240, Glu219 , Tyr237	Ser239, Pro238
11	Erucamide	-105	Glu209	Leu181, His218
12	D- α -Tocopherol	-116	Ser239, Tyr240	Ala182, Leu181 , Tyr210, His218, His222, His228 , Tyr240
13	Trifolin	-105	Ala182 , Tyr240, Glu219 , Tyr237, Pro238	Ser239, His218 , Pro238
14	2-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxy-4H-chromen-4-one	-114	Pro238, Ala182, Glu219 , His222, Arg214	His218 , Tyr240, Leu181, Val215
15	1-Stearoylglycerol	-111	Asn180, Leu181, Ala182, His218, Glu219, Pro238	His218, Val215, Leu181 , Tyr210
16	Hexadecanamide	-99	Val215	Ala182, Val215, Leu181, His218
17	Triethylene glycol monobutyl ether	-91	Tyr210, Tyr240, Glu209, Glu219, Pro238	Val215, His218
18	4-Methoxycinnamaldehyde	-84	His218 , Arg214, Val215, Tyr240, Leu181	His183 , Tyr240, Arg214
19	EGCG	-128	Asn180, Leu181, Ala182 , Glu209, Tyr240, Val215, Glu219 , Tyr237, Gly179	Tyr240, His218 , Tyr240, Leu181, Val215

Bold residues indicate the same interaction with the native ligand methylamino-phenylalanyl-leucyl-hydroxamic acid.

specific amino acids, such as His218, Leu181, and Val215. Hydrophobic interactions are non-covalent forces that occur between non-polar regions of a ligand and the hydrophobic residues of a protein, contributing significantly to the stabilization of the ligand-receptor complex (Patil et al. 2010).

Based on Table 4, among the compounds evaluated against elastase, monoolein exhibited the strongest predicted binding affinity (MolDock score: -139), followed by bilobol (-133) and erucamide (-129). Accordingly, the binding affinity ranking was monoolein > bilobol > erucamide. The docking of the native ligand and EGCG resulted in MolDock scores of -78 and -122, respectively. The docking scores of the three top-ranked compounds were more negative than those of the native ligand and EGCG, suggesting stronger predicted binding affinity. Regarding elastase inhibition, elastase formed a hydrogen bond with amino acid residue Ser195 in the native ligand. EGCG had affinity because it formed hydrogen bonds with the active amino acid residue, Ser195. These findings suggest that interaction with residue Ser195 may not be essential for elastase inhibition, since monoolein, bilobol, and erucamide were able to inhibit its potential despite lacking this interaction. According to Wenas et al. (2025), residue Ser195 is identified as a key component of the elastase catalytic site. Consequently, ligands that interact with this

residue may effectively inhibit the enzyme. Furthermore, monoolein, bilobol, and erucamide interacted with residue Cys220 in the binding pocket, similar to the native ligand. In contrast, EGCG interacted with the His57 residue through hydrophobic interactions, indicating a slightly different binding orientation within the active site. The 2D and 3D interaction structures of collagenase and elastase with their respective ligands are shown in Figs 3, 4.

Bilobol and monoolein demonstrated binding affinity comparable to the positive control for collagenase and elastase, respectively. Both compounds suggest a potential inhibitory mechanism against both enzymes. The number of hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds formed by each compound did not consistently correlate with their respective MolDock scores. Although hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions are primary stabilizing forces, van der Waals and electrostatic interactions also contribute to the binding energy (Shahidi and Dissanayaka 2023). These results align with earlier studies indicating that unsaturated fatty acids function as inhibitors of collagenase and elastase via hydrophobic interactions at the enzyme active site (Sklan et al. 1990; Rennert and Melzig 2002). Moreover, numerous studies have indicated that phenolic compounds function as inhibitors of collagenase and elastase (Wittenauer et al. 2015; Saechan et al. 2021).

Figure 4. Three-dimensional and two-dimensional protein–ligand interactions at the elastase-related active site of compounds from *A. elliptica* leaf extract. A, B. Native ligand 2-(2-hydroxy-cyclopentyl)-pent-4-enal; C, D. Monoolein; E, F. Bilobolol; G, H. Erucaamide; I, J. EGCG.

In this study, docking examined against collagenase inhibition showed that the compounds identified in AET leaf extract exhibited a slightly lower binding affinity than EGCG. However, their values remain within a comparable range, which may be advantageous for the active site. Meanwhile, the IC_{50} value of AET leaf extract was higher than that of the standard in the elastase inhibition assay. Nevertheless, docking studies indicate that several compounds identified in the extract demonstrated stronger binding affinity compared to the native ligand and EGCG. This suggests potential elastase inhibition at the individual compound level, although their concentration in the crude extract may be insufficient for comparable *in vitro* effects. The difference in inhibitory activity between the extract and individual compounds may result from synergistic or antagonistic interactions among the compounds of the extract (Caesar and Cech 2019).

Conclusion

Variations in total phenolic and flavonoid contents among different plant parts of AET influenced the antioxidant activity of the extract, with the leaf extract demonstrating the highest phenolic content and exhibiting strong to very strong antioxidant activity in both DPPH and ABTS assays. Notably, the leaf extract showed inhibitory activities against collagenase ($IC_{50} = 104.11 \pm 11.20 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and elastase ($IC_{50} = 294.67 \pm 8.52 \mu\text{g/mL}$). LC-HRMS revealed that phenolics, flavonoids, and fatty acids are the compounds potentially contributing to these bioactivities. This finding is further supported by molecular docking analysis, which showed favorable binding interactions between selected compounds and the catalytic sites of collagenase and elastase. In particular, bilobolol, monoolein, and α -linolenic acid derived from AET leaf extract exhibited strong affinity for collagenase inhibition, whereas the compounds monoolein,

Table 4. Hydrogen and hydrophobic interactions of target compounds from *A. elliptica* leaf extract with elastase.

No	Ligand	MolDock Score	Interaction	
			Hydrogen	Hydrophobic
1	2-(2-hydroxy-cyclopentyl)-pent-4-enal	-78	Ser195	Cys220
2	α -Linolenic acid	-37	Gly193	Cys191, Cys220 , Cys42, Cys58, His57
3	4-Phenylbutyric acid	-71	Ser195	-
4	1-Linoleylglycerol	-124	Ser217, Asn192, Gly216, Cys220	His40, His57
5	Monoolein	-139	Ser217, Ser226, Tyr221, Gly184, Gly216, Pro225, Cys220, Lys224, Ile188	Cys220 , His57
6	Linolenic acid ethyl ester	-125	Gly193	Cys19, Cys220 , Cys42, Cys58, His57
7	Gallic acid	-66	Ser195 , Ser190	Cys191, Asn192
8	Citric acid	-67	Gly216, Ser195 , His57, Asn192, Gly216	
9	Bilobol	-133	Thr41, His57, Cys58	Val213, Cys220 , His57, Cys42
10	Hyperoside	-107	Ser195 , His57, Ser190, Ser215, Asn147, Gly216, Cys220	-
11	Erucamide	-129	Asn192	Val213, Cys220 , His40, His57
12	D- α -Tocopherol	-119	His57	Cys220 , Leu99, His57
13	Trifolin	-110	Ser195 , Ser190, Ser217, Cys191, Gly216, Ser217	-
14	2-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxy-4H-chromen-4-one	-114	Ser195 , Ser190, Asn192, Ser217	Ser190, Cys191, Cys220
15	1-Stearoylglycerol	-123	Gly216	Val213, Cys220
16	Hexadecanamide	-50	Asn192	Val213
17	Triethylene glycol monobutyl ether	-71	Asn192, Gly193, Gly216, Cys191, Ser195	-
18	4-Methoxycinnamaldehyde	-85	Ser190, Gly219	-
19	EGCG	-122	Ser195 , Gly216, Thr41, Cys42, His57, Cys220, Asn192, Gly219	His57

Bold residues indicate the same interaction with the native ligand 2-(2-hydroxy-cyclopentyl)-pent-4-enal.

bilobol, and erucamide showed strong affinity for elastase inhibition. Collectively, the convergence of phytochemical profiling, *in vitro* assay, and molecular docking analysis supports a multi-target mechanism underlying the antioxidant, anti-collagenase, and anti-elastase properties of AET. Nevertheless, as the identified metabolites remain tentative annotations and authentic reference standards were not employed, future investigations should prioritize compound confirmation, quantitative profiling, and validation in cellular models. These findings indicate that this AET extract is a promising natural candidate with pleiotropic bioactive potential for the development of a phytocosmetic product, specifically targeting skin anti-aging applications.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Research Grant 2025, the Research and Innovation Program for Drugs and Vaccines (CFJRC-ORK2025-95394416929), the Health Research Organization, and the National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), Indonesia. Gratitude is also extended to the Bioprospecting of Indonesian Medicinal Plants Program, a research collaboration between BRIN and the Korea Research Institute of Bioscience and Biotechnology (KRIBB), for providing the research specimens.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

No funding was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
